

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms CHARAN S J of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms LINTOM of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHASHIDHAR G** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018-19**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms AMAN SHETTY of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ANUPALLAVI of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **HRITHIN N.K** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018-19**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RUDRESH M** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018-19**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHRADDHA S K** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018-19**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Adesh Palaneer of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Akash Joseph of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Amaldev P S of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Aneesh Pai B** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Gautam C** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Gopika Ramesan** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms K C Anjana of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Karthik B** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Mahesh Acharya of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Mohammed of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Prakyath B** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Prarthan S of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Preethilatha G of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Rakshan** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Ruthvik S Kunder** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sahithi of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Shibin Varghese** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Shivaprasad B of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Shreyas K N of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sneha of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sreelakshmi of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Sudharshan N** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABHINAV A** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms AMAN RAJATH of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ANIRUDH K of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms CHARANRAJ of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **JIBIN** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **LIKHITH V** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MALAVIKA of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019-20**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NIKIL P AIL of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NISHAN G of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RAKSHAN R** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RAVITH** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **S SRUJAN** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019-20**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHOBITH NAIR** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SPARSHA JAIN** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **USHA T** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Abdul Rehman of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Aadarsh Ajit of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Adhith Raj K of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Akash Vinod of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Amal M Nambiar of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Arjun Baskey of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Aswathi M of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Balanarayanan C** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Bhagath S Das** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Darshan R** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Don Joseph** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Ganesh D Salian of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Goutham Pradeep of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Hadhikh Jasar** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Janani B** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Jidev T K** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Joseph Jiji** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Megha Vinesh of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Mohammed of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Muhammed** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Mohamed Sahal of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Muhammed Fazal of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Nadeem Noushad of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Nidhi Santosh of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms N. Shikha Mallya of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Pratham** of **BSc** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Shaharan Subair** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Shibili Mubarak P** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Smithu K B** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sulaiman N of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Thejas Shetty** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Thejus Praveen of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Vaishak K** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Vinuth** of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Photoshop and Video Editing** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Vishnu K of BSc for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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